
EFFECT OF DIFFERENT LIGHT CONDITIONS ON SEED GERMINATION

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“BEHAVIORAL STUDY OF SEED GERMINATION IN DIFFERENT LIGHT CONDITIONS” by

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Abstract

This study investigates the effect of different light conditions like sunlight, room light, and darkness on seed germination and early seedling growth. Identical seeds were placed under controlled environmental conditions, with light exposure as the only variable. Germination rate, seedlings height, and physical conditions were observed over six days. It is expected that while germination can occur in all conditions, light significantly influences the rate of growth, chlorophyll development, and overall seedling health. The findings of this study help to better understand the role of light in early plant development.

Keyword: Seed germination rate, light exposure effects, photomorphogenesis, seedling development, chlorophyll synthesis, plant growth response, light vs darkness, early plant physiology, environmental growth factors, controlled experiment

Introduction

Seed germination is a fundamental process in the life cycle of plants, during which a seed develops into a new seedling. This process is influenced by several environmental factors, including water, temperature, oxygen, and light. Among these, light plays a crucial role not only in germination for some species but also in the growth and development of seedlings.

Light is essential for photosynthesis, the process by which plants produce food using sunlight. In the absence of light, seedlings may still germinate but often exhibit abnormal growth patterns, such as elongation and lack of green coloration, a condition known as etiolation.

This experiment aims to examine how different light conditions like direct sunlight, room light, and complete darkness which affect the germination rate and early growth of seeds. The study provides insight into the importance of light in plant development.

Materials and Methods

Materials

The following materials were used in this experiment:

- Fenugreek seeds
- Three plastic cups
- Water
- Marker for labeling

Methods

Three groups of seeds were prepared to observe the effect of different light conditions on germination.

Each plastic cup was lined with equal amount of water. Ten Fenugreek seeds were placed in each plastic cup. Care was taken to ensure that all conditions remained constant except for light exposure.

- **Group A (Sunlight):** The plastic cup was placed under direct sunlight.
- **Group B (Room Light):** The plastic cup was kept indoors under normal room lighting conditions.
- **Group C (Dark):** The plastic cup was placed in complete darkness, such as inside a closed box.

The experiment was conducted over a period of six days. Observations were recorded daily, including the number of germinated seeds, seedling average height, and visible physical conditions.

Results

1. Table Representation: The germination of seeds under different light conditions was observed for six days. The results are recorded in the table below.

Table 1: Number of seeds germinated under different light conditions

Day	Sunlight	Room light	Dark
1	0	0	0
2	2	2	1
3	2	2	4
4	2	2	6
5	2	2	6
6	10	2	10

Table 2: Average Height (cm) of seedlings

Day	Sunlight	Room light	Dark
1	0	0	0
2	0.2	0.75	1.5
3	1.5	5.1	3.15
4	1.85	6.65	4.06
5	2.3	7.25	5.43
6	1.82	7.45	5.96

Table 3: Physical conditions of seedlings

Day	Sunlight	Room light	Dark
1	Nothing Observe	Nothing Observe	Nothing Observe
2	Healthy and small seedlings	Moderately weak and tall seedlings	Weak and tall seedlings
3	Healthy but small seedlings	Moderately weak and tall seedlings	Weak and tall seedlings
4	Healthy but small seedlings	Moderately weak and tall seedlings	Weak and very tall seedlings
5	Healthy but small seedlings	Moderately weak and tall seedlings	Weak and very tall seedlings
6	Much healthy but normal height	Moderately weak and tall seedlings	Weak, yellowish and very tall seedlings

Comparison of Tables

From **Table 1**, it is observed that seed germination occurred in all three conditions. However, seeds in darkness and sunlight showed higher germination by Day 6 (10 seeds), while room light showed very low germination (only 2 seeds).

From **Table 2**, the average height of seedlings varied significantly. Seedlings grown in room light showed the highest height (up to 7.45 cm), followed by dark conditions (5.96 cm), while sunlight showed comparatively lower height.

From **Table 3**, the physical condition of seedlings differed clearly. Seedlings in sunlight were healthy and strong with normal growth. In contrast, seedlings grown in darkness were weak, very tall, and yellowish. Room light seedlings showed moderate growth but were weaker than sunlight-grown plants.

Overall, the tables show that while darkness and room light promote elongation, sunlight supports healthier and stronger plant development.

2. Graph Representation: The germination of seeds under different light conditions was observed for six days. The results are showed by graph below for better visualization.

Graph 1: Number of seeds germinated under different light conditions

Graph 2: Average Height (cm) of seedlings

Graphical Comparison

The graphs provide a clear visual understanding of the results.

The **first graph (Germination graph)** shows that germination increased over time in all conditions. Darkness and sunlight reached maximum germination by Day 6, while room light remained significantly lower throughout the experiment.

The **second graph (Height graph)** shows that seedling height increased rapidly in room light and dark conditions compared to sunlight. However, despite greater height, these seedlings were weaker.

Calculations

1. Germination Percentage

The germination percentage was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Germination Percentage} = (\text{Number of Germinated Seeds} / \text{Total Number of Seeds}) \times 100$$

Total number of seeds = 10

Using day six data:

- Sunlight = $(10 / 10) \times 100 = \mathbf{100\%}$
- Room light = $(2 / 10) \times 100 = \mathbf{20\%}$
- Dark = $(10 / 10) \times 100 = \mathbf{100\%}$

2. Average Seedling Height

Average Length = (Total Height of all seedlings / Total number of seedlings)

Using day six data:

- Sunlight = **1.82 cm**
- Room light = **7.45 cm**
- Dark = **5.96 cm**

3. Growth Increase

Growth Increase = (Final Length – Initial Length)

Initial length (Day 1) = 0 cm

Day six growth of sunlight, room light & dark = 1.82, 7.45 & 5.96

- Sunlight = $1.82 - 0 = \mathbf{1.82\text{ cm}}$
- Room light = $7.45 - 0 = \mathbf{7.45\text{ cm}}$
- Dark = $5.96 - 0 = \mathbf{5.96\text{ cm}}$

Summary of Calculations

The results show that sunlight and dark conditions had the highest germination percentage (100%), while room light had the lowest (20%). However, the highest growth in length was observed in room light, followed by dark conditions.

Overall Result

From the experiment, it is clear that seeds can germinate in all light conditions. However, light plays an important role in the quality of growth.

Darkness and room light promote rapid elongation, but the seedlings are weak and pale. On the other hand, sunlight produces shorter but healthier and stronger seedlings.

Discussion

The results of this experiment show that light has a significant effect on the growth of seedlings. Although seeds were able to germinate in all three conditions, differences were observed in their growth and development.

Seeds kept in sunlight produced green and healthy seedlings. This is because sunlight is necessary for photosynthesis and proper development. On the other hand, seedlings grown in darkness were taller but weak and pale in color. This happens due to the absence of light, a condition known as etiolation.

Seeds kept under room light showed moderate growth, which was not as healthy as sunlight but better than complete darkness. Therefore, light plays an important role in the quality of plant growth.

Conclusion

From this experiment, it can be concluded that seeds can germinate under different light conditions. However, light is essential for healthy growth and development of seedlings.

Seedlings grown in sunlight were strong and green, while those grown in darkness were weak and pale. Thus, proper light is necessary for normal plant growth.

Limitations

Some limitations were present in this experiment. The number of seeds used was small, which may affect the accuracy of the results. It was also difficult to keep all environmental conditions exactly the same for each group.

In addition, measurement of seedling length may have small errors due to manual observation. More accurate results could be obtained by using better measuring tools and repeating the experiment.

Recommendations

This experiment can be improved by using a larger number of seeds to obtain more accurate results. It can also be repeated with different types of seeds.

Further studies can be done by changing light intensity or duration to better understand the effect of light on plant growth.

References

1. Saha, J. K. *Plant Anatomy and Embryology*.
2. Ray, J. N. *Plant Physiology*.
3. Khan Academy. (n.d.). Seed germination and plant growth. Retrieved from <https://www.khanacademy.org>
4. Wikipedia. (n.d.). Seed germination. Retrieved from <https://www.wikipedia.org>

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